

Collateral Impact on Derivative Pricing

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ABSTRACT

This article makes a theoretical and empirical contribution to the study of collateralization by addressing several essential questions concerning the posting of collateral. We find evidence that financial institutions are sprinting to comply with the Dodd-Frank Act. In the new practice, contracts are continuously negotiated over-the-counter as usual, but cleared and settled via clearinghouses, as clearinghouses claim that cleared contracts would be economically equivalent to their OTC counterparts. As a result, swap premia in cleared market are determined in a similar way to those in OTC markets. We argue that this practice may not be appropriate because we notice that the clearing mechanics of a clearinghouse change the risk structure and thereby the asset prices. In fact, we find that cleared derivatives are not economically equivalent to their OTC counterparts.

Key words: collateralization, asset pricing, plumbing of the financial system, swap premium spread, OTC/cleared/listed financial markets.

1. Introduction

The reason collateralization of financial derivatives and repos has become one of the most important and widespread credit risk mitigation techniques is that the Bankruptcy Code contains a series of “safe harbor” provisions to exempt these contracts from the “automatic stay”. The automatic stay prohibits the creditors from undertaking any act that threatens the debtor’s asset, while the safe harbor, a luxury, permits the creditors to terminate derivative and repo contracts with the debtor in bankruptcy and to seize the underlying collateral. This paper focuses on safe harbor contracts (e.g., derivatives and repos), but many of the points made are equally applicable to automatic stay contracts.

Financial derivatives can be categorized into three types. The first category is over-the-counter (OTC) derivatives, which are customized two-way agreements. The second group is cleared derivatives, which are negotiated two-wayly but booked with a clearinghouse. Finally, the third type is exchange-traded/listed derivatives, which are executed over an exchange. The differences between the three types are described in detail on the International Swap Dealers Association (ISDA) website (see ISDA (2013)).

Under the new regulations (e.g., Dodd-Frank Wall Street Reform Act), certain ‘eligible’ OTC derivatives must be cleared with central counterparties (CCPs) (see Heller and Vause (2012), Pirrong (2011), etc.). Hull (2011) further recommends mandatory CCP clearing of all OTC derivatives. Meanwhile, Duffie and Zhu (2011) suggest a move toward the joint clearing of interest rate swaps and credit default swaps (CDS) in the same clearinghouse.

There are three types of collateralization: full, partial or over. Full-collateralization is a process where the posting of collateral is equal to the current mark-to-market (MTM) value. Partial/under-collateralization is a process where the posting of collateral is less than the current MTM value. Over-collateralization is a process where the posting of collateral is greater than the current MTM value.

From the perspective of collateral obligations, collateral arrangements can be one-way or two-way. In a one-way arrangement, only one predefined counterparty has the right to call for collateral. One-way agreements are generally used when the other counterparty is much less creditworthy. In a two-way arrangement, on the other hand, both counterparties have the right to call for collateral.

Upon default and early termination, the values due under the ISDA Master Agreement are determined. These amounts are then netted and a single net payment is made. All of the collateral on hand would be available to satisfy this total amount, up to the full value of that collateral. In other words, the collateral to be posted is calculated on the basis of the aggregated value of the portfolio, but not on the basis of any individual transaction.

The use of collateral in financial markets has increased sharply over the past decade, yet analytical and empirical research on collateralization is relatively sparse. The effect of collateralization on financial contracts is an understudied area. Collateral management is often carried out in an ad-hoc manner, without reference to an analytical framework. Comparatively little research has been done to analytically and empirically assess the economic significance and implications of collateralization. Such a quantitative and empirical analysis is the primary contribution of this paper.

Due to the complexity of quantifying collateralization, previous studies seem to turn away from direct and detailed modeling of collateralization (see Fujii and Takahashi (2012)). For example, Johannes and Sundareshan (2007), and Fujii and Takahashi (2012) characterize collateralization via a cost-of-collateral instantaneous rate (or stochastic dividend or convenience yield). Piterbarg (2010) regards collateral as a regular asset in a portfolio and uses the replication approach to price collateralized contracts. All of the previous works focus on full-collateralization only.

This article makes a theoretical and empirical contribution to the study of collateralization by addressing several essential questions concerning the posting of collateral. First, how does collateralization affect expected asset prices? To answer this question, we develop a comprehensive analytical framework for pricing financial contracts under different (partial/full/over and one-way /two-way) collateral arrangements in different (OTC/cleared/listed) markets.

In contrast to other collateralization models in current literature, we characterize a collateral process directly based on the fundamental principal and legal structure of the CSA agreement. A model is devised that allows for collateralization adhering to bankruptcy laws. As such, the model can back out differences in prices due to counterparty risk. This framework is very useful for valuing off-the-run or outstanding

financial contracts subject to credit risk and collateralization, where the price quotes are not available. Given this model, we are able to explain credit-related spreads and provide an important tool for credit value adjustment (CVA).

Our theoretical analysis shows that collateralization can always improve recovery and reduce credit risk. If a contract is over-collateralized (e.g., a repo or cleared contract), its value is equal to the risk-free value. If a contract is partially collateralized (e.g., an OTC derivatives), its CSA value is less than the risk-free value but greater than the non-CSA risky value.

Second, how can the model be empirically verified? To achieve the verification goal, this paper empirically measures the effect of collateralization on pricing and compares it with model-implied prices. This calls for data on financial contracts that have different collateral arrangements but are similar otherwise. We use a unique interest rate swap contract data set from an investment bank for the empirical study, as interest rate swaps collectively account for around two-thirds of both the notional and market value of all outstanding derivatives.

Unlike the generic mid-market swap rates, swap premia are determined in a competitive market according to the basic principles of supply and demand. A client who wants to enter a swap contract first contacts a number of swap dealers and asks for a swap rate. After comparing all quotations, the client chooses the most competitive rate. A swap premium is supposed to cover operational, liquidity, funding, and credit costs as well as a profit margin. If the premium is too low, the dealer may lose money. If the premium is too high, the dealer may lose the competitive advantage.

Empirically, we find quite a number of CSA swap pairs in the data, where the two contracts in each pair have different counterparties but are otherwise the same. The test results demonstrate that the model-implied swap premium spreads are very close to the market swap premium spreads, indicating that the model is quite accurate.

Third, what are the effects of counterparty risk and collateralization, alone or combined, on swap premium spreads? We first study the marginal impact of counterparty risk on spreads. CDS premia (the prices of insuring against a firm's default) theoretically reflect the credit risk of the firm. Presumably,

differences in CDS premia should be largely attributable to differences in counterparty risk. We estimate a regression model where market swap premium spreads are used as the dependent variable and differences between CDS premia as the explanatory variable. The estimation results show that the adjusted R^2 is 0.7472, implying that approximately 75% of market premium spreads can be explained by CDS spreads. In other words, counterparty risk alone can provide a good but not overwhelming prediction on spreads.

Next, we assess the joint effect of both counterparty risk and collateralization on premium spreads. Since the model-generated swap premium spreads take into account both counterparty risk and collateralization, we present another regression model where the market swap premium spreads are regressed on the implied swap premium spreads. The estimation results show that the constant term is insignificantly different from zero; the slope coefficient is close to 1 and the adjusted R^2 is very high. This suggests that the implied premium spreads explains nearly all of the market premium spreads.

Finally, how does collateralization impact pricing in different markets? Our proprietary data reveal that cleared swaps have dramatically increased since 2011, reflecting the financial institutions' compliance to regulatory requirements. We find evidence that the economical determination of swap rates in cleared markets is the same as that in OTC markets, as all clearinghouses claim that cleared derivatives would replicate OTC derivatives, and promise that transactions through the clearinghouses would be economically equivalent to similar transactions handled in OTC markets.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 discusses one-way collateralization. Section 3 elaborates two-way collateralization. Section 4 presents empirical evidence. The conclusions and discussion are provided in Section 5. All proofs and some detailed derivations are contained in the appendices.

2. One-way Collateralization

A one-way collateral arrangement is sometimes used when a higher-rated counterparty deals with a lower-rated counterparty, in which only one party, normally the lower-rated one, is required to deliver

collateral to guarantee performance under the agreement. Typical examples of one-wayly collateralized contracts include: repos, cleared/listed derivatives, sovereign derivatives (see [AFME-ICMA-ISDA \(2011\)](#)), and some OTC derivatives¹.

Since the only reason for taking collateral is to reduce/eliminate credit risk, collateralization analysis is closely related to credit risk modeling. There are two primary types of models that attempt to describe default processes in the literature: structural models and reduced-form models. Many people in the market have tended to gravitate toward the reduced-form models given their mathematical tractability and market consistency. In the reduced-form framework, the stopping (or default) time τ of a firm is modeled as a Cox arrival process (also known as a doubly stochastic Poisson process) whose first jump occurs at default and is defined by,

$$\tau = \inf \left\{ t : \int_0^t h(s, \Gamma_s) ds \geq \Delta \right\} \quad (1)$$

where $h(t)$ or $h(t, \Gamma_t)$ denotes the stochastic hazard rate or arrival intensity dependent on an exogenous common state Γ_t , and Δ is a unit exponential random variable independent of Γ_t .

It is well-known that the survival probability from time t to s in this framework is defined by

$$p(t, s) := P(\tau > s | \tau > t) = \exp\left(-\int_t^s h(u) du\right) \quad (2a)$$

The default probability for the period (t, s) in this framework is given by

$$q(t, s) := P(\tau \leq s | \tau > t) = 1 - p(t, s) = 1 - \exp\left(-\int_t^s h(u) du\right) \quad (2b)$$

In order to assess the impact of collateralization on pricing, we study valuation with and without collateralization respectively.

2.1 Valuation without collateralization

¹ Our CSA data from two investment banks show that 8.92% of CSA counterparties are subject to one-way collateralization

Let valuation date be t . Consider a financial contract that promises to pay a $X_T > 0$ from party B to party A at maturity date T , and nothing before date T . We suppose that party A and party B do not have a CSA agreement. All calculations are from the perspective of party A . The risk free value of the financial contract is given by

$$V^F(t) = E[D(t, T)X_T | \mathcal{F}_t] \quad (3a)$$

where

$$D(t, T) = \exp\left[-\int_t^T r(u)du\right] \quad (3b)$$

where $E\{\bullet | \mathcal{F}_t\}$ is the expectation conditional on the \mathcal{F}_t , $D(t, T)$ denotes the risk-free discount factor at time t for the maturity T and $r(u)$ denotes the risk-free short rate at time u ($t \leq u \leq T$).

Next, we discuss risky valuation. In a one-way credit risk case, we assume that party A is default-free and party B is defaultable. We divide the time period (t, T) into n very small time intervals (Δt) . In our derivation, we use the approximation $\exp(y) \approx 1 + y$ provided that y is very small. The survival and default probabilities of party B for the period $(t, t + \Delta t)$ are given by

$$\hat{p}(t) := p(t, t + \Delta t) = \exp(-h(t)\Delta t) \approx 1 - h(t)\Delta t \quad (4a)$$

$$\hat{q}(t) := q(t, t + \Delta t) = 1 - \exp(-h(t)\Delta t) \approx h(t)\Delta t \quad (4b)$$

The non-CSA value of the contract at time t is the discounted expectation of all possible payoffs and is given by

$$V^N(t) = E\left\{\exp(-r(t)\Delta t) [\hat{p}(t) + \varphi(t)\hat{q}(t)] V^N(t + \Delta t) | \mathcal{F}_t\right\} \approx E\left\{\exp(-b(t)\Delta t) V^N(t + \Delta t) | \mathcal{F}_t\right\} \quad (5)$$

where $b(t) = r(t) + h(t)(1 - \varphi(t)) = r(t) + s(t)$ denotes the (short) risky rate and $s(t) = h(t)(1 - \varphi(t))$ denotes the (short) credit spread.

Similarly, we have

$$V^N(t + \Delta t) = E\left\{\exp(-b(t + \Delta t)\Delta t) V^N(t + 2\Delta t) | \mathcal{F}_{t+\Delta t}\right\} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
V^N(t) &= E\left\{\exp(-b(t)\Delta t)V^N(t+\Delta t)|\mathcal{F}_t\right\} = E\left\{\exp(-b(t)\Delta t)E\left[\exp(-b(t+\Delta t)\Delta t)V^N(t+2\Delta t)|\mathcal{F}_{t+\Delta t}\right]|\mathcal{F}_t\right\} \\
&= E\left\{\exp\left(-\sum_{i=0}^1 b(t+i\Delta t)\Delta t\right)V^N(t+2\Delta t)|\mathcal{F}_t\right\}
\end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

By recursively deriving from t forward over T where $V^N(T) = X_T$ and taking the limit as Δt approaches zero, the non-CSA value of the contract can be obtained as

$$V^N(t) = E\left\{\exp\left[-\int_t^T b(u)du\right]X_T|\mathcal{F}_t\right\} \tag{8}$$

We may think of $b(u)$ as the risk-adjusted short rate. Equation (8) is the same as Equation (10) in Duffie and Singleton (1999), which is the market model for pricing risky bonds.

If we assume that a default may occur only on the payment date, the non-CSA value of the instrument in the discrete-time setting is given by

$$V^N(t) = E\left\{D(t,T)[p(t,T) + \varphi(T)q(t,T)]X_T|\mathcal{F}_t\right\} = E\left\{I(t,T)X_T|\mathcal{F}_t\right\} \tag{9}$$

where $I(t,T) = D(t,T)[p(t,T) + \varphi(T)q(t,T)]$ can be regarded as a risk-adjusted discount factor.

The difference between the risk-free value and the risky value is known as the *credit value adjustment* (CVA). CVA is required by regulators, such as, International Accounting Standard Board (IASB) and Basel committee. The CVA reflects the market value of counterparty risk or the cost of protection required to hedge counterparty risk and is given by

$$CVA(t) = V^F(t) - V^N(t) = E\left\{D(t,T)[q(t,T)(1 - \varphi(T))]|X_T|\mathcal{F}_t\right\} \tag{10}$$

Since the recovery rate is always less than 1, we have $CVA(t) > 0$ or $V^N(t) < V^F$. In other words, the risky value is always less than the risk-free value. An intuitive explanation is that credit risk makes a financial contract less valuable.

2.2 Valuation with collateralization

The posting of collateral is regulated by the CSA that specifies a variety of terms including the threshold, the independent amount, and the minimum transfer amount (MTA), etc. The threshold is the unsecured credit exposure that a party is willing to bear. The MTA is used to avoid the workload associated

with a frequent transfer of insignificant amounts of collateral. The independent amount plays the same role as the initial margin (or haircut).

Suppose that there is a one-way CSA agreement between parties A and B in which only party B is required to deliver collateral when the mark-to-market (MTM) value arises over the collateral threshold H .

The choice of modeling assumptions for collateralization should be based on the legal structure of collateral agreements. According to the Bankruptcy Law, if the collateral value is greater than the default claim, creditors can only have a claim on the collateral up to the full amount of their default demand. Any excess collateral is returned to the estate of the failed institution for the payment of unsecured creditors. If the demand for default payment exceeds the collateral value, the balance of the demand will be treated as an unsecured claim and subject to its pro rate distribution under the Bankruptcy Code's priority scheme (see Garlson (1992), Routh and Douglas (2005), and Edwards and Morrison (2005)). The default payment under a collateral agreement, therefore, can be mathematically expressed as

$$P^D(T) = \begin{cases} X_T & \text{if } C(T) \geq X_T \\ C(T) + \varphi(T)(X_T - C(T)) = \varphi(T)X_T + C(T)(1 - \varphi(T)) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (11a)$$

or

$$P^D(T) = 1_{X_T \leq C(T)} X_T + 1_{X_T > C(T)} [C(T) + \varphi(T)(X_T - C(T))] \quad (11b)$$

where 1_Y is an indicator function that is equal to one if Y is true and zero otherwise, and $C(T)$ is the collateral amount at time T .

It is worth noting that the default payment in equation (11) is always greater than the original recovery, i.e., $P^D(T) > \varphi(T)X_T$, since $\varphi(T)$ is always less than 1. Said differently, the default payoff of a CSA contract is always greater than the default payoff of the same contract without a CSA agreement. That is why *the major benefit of collateralization should be viewed as an improved recovery in the event of a default.*

Let us consider repo/cleared/listed markets first. Contracts in these markets are always over collateralized, as the parties with collateral obligation are required to deposit initial margins and are also

charged variation margins in response to changes in the market values. The total collateral (initial margin plus variation margin) posted at time t is given by

$$C(t) = V^C(t) - H(t) \quad (12)$$

where $V^C(t)$ is the CSA value of the contract at time t and $H(t)$ is the effective threshold. Note that for over-collateralization, the effective threshold is negative, i.e., $H(t) < 0$, which equals the negative initial margin. The collateral in equation (12) is a linear function of the asset value.

At time T , if the contract survives with probability $p(t, T)$, the survival value is the promised payoff X_T and the collateral taker returns the collateral to the collateral provider. If the contract defaults with probability $q(t, T)$, the collateral taker has recourse to the collateral and obtains a default payment up to the full value of the promised payoff X_T . The remaining collateral $C(T) - X_T$ returns to the collateral provider. The CSA value of the over collateralized contract is the discounted expectation of the payoffs and is given by

$$V^C(t) = E[D(t, T)(q(t, T)X_T + p(t, T)X_T) | \mathcal{F}_t] = V^F(t) \quad (13)$$

Equation (13) tells us that *the CSA value of an over-collateralized contract is equal to the risk-free value*. This result is consistent with the market practice in which market participants commonly assume that repos and cleared contracts are virtually free of default risk because of the implicit guarantee of the contracts provided by the clearinghouse and backup collateral.

Next, we turn to OTC markets. We obtain the CSA data from two investment banks. The data show that 61.32% of CSA counterparties have a zero threshold, and the remaining 38.68% use a positive threshold ranging from 25,000 to 750,000,000. Moreover, all CSA counterparties in the data maintain a positive MTA ranging from 500 to 60,000,000, which means that the effective thresholds are always greater than zero, i.e., $H(t) > 0$. If the value of the contract $V^C(t)$ is less than the effective threshold $H(t)$, no collateral is posted; otherwise, the required collateral is equal to the difference between the contract value and the effective threshold. The collateral amount posted at time t can be expressed mathematically as

$$C(t) = \begin{cases} V^C(t) - H(t) & \text{if } V^C(t) > H(t) \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (14a)$$

or

$$C(t) = 1_{V^C(t) > H(t)} (V^C(t) - H(t)) \quad (14b)$$

Since all CSA derivatives in OTC markets are partially collateralized, the default claim is almost certainly greater than the collateral amount. For a discrete one-period (t, T) economy, the collateral amount $C(t)$ posted at time t is defined in (14). At time T , if the contract survives, the survival value is the promised payoff X_T and the collateral taker returns the collateral to the collateral provider. If the contract defaults, the collateral taker possesses the collateral. The portion of the default claim that exceeds the collateral value is treated as an unsecured claim. Thus, the default payment is $C(T) + \varphi(T)(X_T - C(T))$, where $C(T) = C(t) / D(t, T)$ is the future value of the collateral. Since the most predominant form of collateral is cash according to ISDA (2012), it is reasonable to consider the time value of money only for collateral assets. The large use of cash means that collateral is both liquid and not subject to large fluctuations in value. It can be seen from this, that collateral does not have any bearing on survival payoffs; instead, it takes effect on default payments only. The CSA value of the partially collateralized contract is the discounted expectation of all the payoffs and is given by

$$V^C(t) = E\{D(t, T)[q(t, T)(C(T) + \varphi(T)(X_T - C(T))) + p(t, T)X_T] | \mathcal{F}_t\} \quad (15)$$

Suppose that default probabilities are uncorrelated with interest rates and payoffs². We have the following proposition after some simple mathematics.

Proposition 1: *The one-way CSA value of the partially collateralized single-payment contract is given by*

² Moody's Investor's Service (2000) presents statistics that suggest that the correlations between interest rates, default probabilities and recovery rates are very small and provides a reasonable comfort level for the uncorrelated assumption.

$$V^C(t) = E[F(t, T)X_T | \mathcal{F}_t] - G(t, T) \quad (16a)$$

where

$$F(t, T) = \left(1_{V^N(t) \leq H(t)} + 1_{V^N(t) > H(t)} / \bar{I}(t, T) \right) I(t, T) D(t, T) \quad (16b)$$

$$G(t, T) = 1_{V^N(t) > H(t)} H(t) \bar{q}(t, T) (1 - \varphi(T)) / \bar{I}(t, T) \quad (16c)$$

where $\bar{I}(t, T) = E(I(t, T) | \mathcal{F}_t)$. $I(t, T)$ and $V^N(t)$ are defined in (9).

Proof: See the Appendix.

We may think of $F(t, T)$ as the one-wayly CSA-adjusted discount factor and $G(t, T)$ as the cost of bearing unsecured credit risk. Proposition 1 tells us that the value of the one-wayly collateralized contract is equal to the present value of the payoff discounted by the one-wayly CSA-adjusted discount factors minus the cost of taking unsecured counterparty risk.

The valuation in equation (16) is relatively straightforward. We first compute $V^N(t)$ and then test whether its value is greater than $H(t)$. After that, the calculations of $F(t, T)$, $G(t, T)$ and $V^C(t)$ are easily obtained.

We discuss the following two cases. Case 1: $H(t) = 0$ corresponds to full-collateralization. We have $V^C(t) = V^F(t)$ according to (16) where $H(t) = 0$ and $V^N(t) > 0$. That is to say: the CSA value under full-collateralization is equal to the risk-free value, which is in line with the results of Johannes and Sundaesan (2007), Fujii and Takahashi (2012), and Piterbarg (2010). Due to the mathematical tractability and simplicity, previous modeling works focus on full-collateralization only. As we point out above, however, full-collateralization does not appear to exist in any markets.

Case 2: $H(t) > 0$ represents partial-collateralization. Equation (16) yields $V^N(t) \leq V^C(t) < V^F(t)$ when $H > 0$. In particular, $V^N(t) = V^C(t)$ when $H \rightarrow \infty$. Therefore, we conclude that the CSA value under partial-collateralization is less than the risk-free value but greater than the non-CSA value. Partial-collateralization that reflects the risk tolerance and commercial intent of firms is mostly seen in OTC markets.

Proposition 1 can be easily extended from one-period to multiple-periods. Suppose that a defaultable portfolio/contract has m netted cash flows. Let the m cash flows be represented as $X_i > 0$ with payment dates T_i , where $i = 1, \dots, m$. We derive the following proposition:

Proposition 2: *The one-way CSA value of the partially collateralized multiple-payment contract is given by*

$$V^C(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m E \left[\prod_{j=0}^{i-1} (F(T_j, T_{j+1})) X_i \mid \mathcal{F}_t \right] - \sum_{i=0}^{m-1} E \left[\prod_{j=0}^{i-1} (F(T_j, T_{j+1})) G(T_i, T_{i+1}) \mid \mathcal{F}_t \right] \quad (17a)$$

where

$$F(T_j, T_{j+1}) = \left(1_{J(T_j, T_{j+1}) \leq H(T_j)} + 1_{J(T_j, T_{j+1}) > H(T_j)} / \bar{I}(T_j, T_{j+1}) \right) I(T_j, T_{j+1}) D(T_j, T_{j+1}) \quad (17b)$$

$$G(T_j, T_{j+1}) = 1_{J(T_j, T_{j+1}) > H(T_j)} H(T_j) \bar{q}(T_j, T_{j+1}) (1 - \varphi(T_{j+1})) / \bar{I}(T_j, T_{j+1}) \quad (17c)$$

$$J(T_j, T_{j+1}) = E \left[D(T_j, T_{j+1}) I(T_j, T_{j+1}) (V^C(T_{j+1}) + X_{j+1}) \mid \mathcal{F}_{T_j} \right] \quad (17d)$$

Proof: See the Appendix.

3. Two-way Collateralization

Two counterparties are denoted as A and B . The binomial default rule considers only two possible states: default or survival. Therefore, the default indicator Y_j for party j ($j=A, B$) follows a Bernoulli distribution, which takes value 1 with default probability q_j and value 0 with survival probability p_j , i.e., $P\{Y_j = 0\} = p_j$ and $P\{Y_j = 1\} = q_j$. The marginal default distributions can be determined by the reduced-form models. The joint distributions of a bivariate Bernoulli variable can be easily obtained via the marginal distributions by introducing extra correlations.

Consider a pair of random variables (Y_A, Y_B) that has a bivariate Bernoulli distribution. The joint probability representations are given by

$$p_{00} := P(Y_A = 0, Y_B = 0) = p_A p_B + \sigma_{AB} \quad (18a)$$

$$p_{01} := P(Y_A = 0, Y_B = 1) = p_A q_B - \sigma_{AB} \quad (18b)$$

$$p_{10} := P(Y_A = 1, Y_B = 0) = q_A p_B - \sigma_{AB} \quad (18c)$$

$$p_{11} := P(Y_A = 1, Y_B = 1) = q_A q_B + \sigma_{AB} \quad (18d)$$

where $E(Y_j) = q_j$, $\sigma_j^2 = p_j q_j$, $\sigma_{AB} := E[(Y_A - q_A)(Y_B - q_B)] = \rho_{AB} \sigma_A \sigma_B = \rho_{AB} \sqrt{q_A p_A q_B p_B}$ where ρ_{AB} denotes the default correlation coefficient and σ_{AB} denotes the default covariance.

For a two-way CSA, each party has an effective collateral threshold and is required to post collateral to the other as exposures arise. The collateral amount at t is given by

$$C(t) = \begin{cases} V^C(t) - H_B & \text{if } V^C(t) > H_B \\ 0 & \text{if } H_A \leq V^C(t) \leq H_B \\ V^C(t) - H_A & \text{if } V^C(t) < H_A \end{cases} \quad (19a)$$

or

$$C(t) = 1_{V(t) > H_B} (V^C(t) - H_B) + 1_{V(t) < H_A} (V^C(t) - H_A) \quad (19b)$$

where $H_B \geq 0$ and $H_A \leq 0$ are the collateral thresholds for parties B and A , and $V^C(t)$ is the CSA value of the contract at time t .

At time T , there are a total of four ($2^2 = 4$) possible states shown in Table 1. The CSA value of the contract is the discounted expectation of the payoffs and is given by the following proposition.

Proposition 3: *The two-way CSA value of the partially collateralized single-payment contract is given by*

$$V^C(t) = E[L(t, T) X_T | \mathcal{F}_t] - M(t, T) \quad (20a)$$

where

$$L(t, T) = D(t, T) \left[1_{0 \leq V_B^N(t) \leq H_B(t)} I_B(t, T) + 1_{V_B^N(t) > H_B(t)} I_B(t, T) / \bar{I}_B(t, T) \right. \\ \left. + 1_{0 \geq V_A^N(t) \geq H_A(t)} I_A(t, T) + 1_{V_A^N(t) < H_A(t)} I_A(t, T) / \bar{I}_A(t, T) \right] \quad (20b)$$

$$M(t, T) = 1_{V_B^N(t) > H_B(t)} H_B(t) \bar{q}_B(t, T) (1 - \varphi_B(T)) / \bar{I}_B(t, T) \\ + 1_{V_A^N(t) < H_A(t)} H_A(t) \bar{q}_A(t, T) (1 - \varphi_A(T)) / \bar{I}_A(t, T) \quad (20c)$$

where $\bar{I}_j(t, T) = E[I_j(t, T) | \mathcal{F}_t] = E(p_j(t, T) + \varphi_j(T) q_j(t, T) | \mathcal{F}_t)$, $V_j^N(t) = E[I_j(t, T) X_T | \mathcal{F}_t]$, and $j = A$ or B .

Proof: See the Appendix.

We may consider $L(t,T)$ as the two-wayly CSA-adjusted discount factor and $M(t,T)$ as the cost of bearing unsecured credit risk. Proposition 3 says that the value of the two-wayly collateralized contract is equal to the present value of the payoff discounted by the two-wayly CSA-adjusted discount factor minus the cost of taking unsecured counterparty risk.

Table 1. Payoffs of a two-wayly collateralized contract

This table displays all possible payoffs at time T . In the case of $X_T > 0$, there are a total of four possible states at time T : i) Both A and B survive with probability p_{00} . The contract value is equal to the payoff X_T . ii) A defaults but B survives with probability p_{10} . The contract value is also the payoff X_T . Here we follow the two-way payment rule³. iii) A survives but B defaults with probability p_{01} . The contract value is the collateralized default payment: $C(T) + \varphi_B(T)(X_T - C(T))$. iv) Both A and B default with probability p_{11} . The contract value is also $C(T) + \varphi_B(T)(X_T - C(T))$. A similar logic applies to the case of $X_T < 0$.

State		$Y_A = 0, Y_B = 0$	$Y_A = 1, Y_B = 0$	$Y_A = 0, Y_B = 1$	$Y_A = 1, Y_B = 1$
Comments		A & B survive	A defaults, B survives	A survives, B defaults	A & B default
Probability		p_{00}	p_{10}	p_{01}	p_{11}
Payoff	$X_T > 0$	X_T	X_T	$C(T) + \varphi_B(T)(X_T - C(T))$	$C(T) + \varphi_B(T)(X_T - C(T))$
	$X_T < 0$	X_T	$C(T) + \varphi_A(T)(X_T - C(T))$	X_T	$C(T) + \varphi_A(T)(X_T - C(T))$

³ There are two default settlement rules in the market. The *one-way payment rule* was specified by the early ISDA master agreement. The non-defaulting party is not obligated to compensate the defaulting party if the remaining market value of the instrument is positive for the defaulting party. The *two-way payment rule* is based on current ISDA documentation. The non-defaulting party will pay the full market value of the instrument to the defaulting party if the contract has positive value to the defaulting party.

In particular, if $H_A = H_B = 0$ (corresponding to two-way full-collateralization), and $I_i(t, T)$ and X_T are uncorrelated, we have $L(t, T) = 1$, $M(t, T) = 0$, and thereby $V^C(t) = V^F(t)$. That is to say, under full-collateralization the two-way CSA value of the contract is equal to the risk-free value.

Using a similar derivation as in Proposition 2, we can easily extend Proposition 3 from one-period to multiple-periods. Suppose that a defaultable portfolio/contract has m netted cash flows. Let the m cash flows be represented as X_i with payment dates T_i , where $i = 1, \dots, m$. Each cash flow may be positive or negative. The two-way CSA value of the multiple payment contract is given by

$$V^C(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m E \left[\prod_{k=0}^{i-1} (L(T_k, T_{k+1})) X_i \mid \mathcal{F}_t \right] - \sum_{i=0}^{m-1} E \left[\prod_{k=0}^{i-1} (L(T_k, T_{k+1})) M(T_i, T_{i+1}) \mid \mathcal{F}_t \right] \quad (21a)$$

where

$$L(T_k, T_{k+1}) = D(T_k, T_{k+1}) \left[1_{0 \leq O_B(T_k, T_{k+1}) \leq H_B(T_k)} I_B(T_k, T_{k+1}) + 1_{O_B(T_k, T_{k+1}) > H_B(T_k)} I_B(T_k, T_{k+1}) / \bar{I}_B(T_k, T_{k+1}) \right. \\ \left. + 1_{0 \geq O_A(T_k, T_{k+1}) \geq H_A(T_k)} I_A(T_k, T_{k+1}) + 1_{O_A(T_k, T_{k+1}) < H_A(T_k)} I_A(T_k, T_{k+1}) / \bar{I}_A(T_k, T_{k+1}) \right] \quad (21b)$$

$$M(T_k, T_{k+1}) = 1_{O_B(T_k, T_{k+1}) > H_B(T_k)} H_B(T_k) \bar{q}_B(T_k, T_{k+1}) (1 - \varphi_B(T_{k+1})) / \bar{I}_B(T_k, T_{k+1}) \\ + 1_{O_A(T_k, T_{k+1}) < H_A(T_k)} H_A(T_k) \bar{q}_A(T_k, T_{k+1}) (1 - \varphi_A(T_{k+1})) / \bar{I}_A(T_k, T_{k+1}) \quad (21c)$$

where $O_j(T_k, T_{k+1}) = E \left[D(T_k, T_{k+1}) I_B(T_k, T_{k+1}) (V^C(T_{k+1}) + X_{k+1}) \mid \mathcal{F}_{T_k} \right]$ and $j = A$ or B .

Similar to Proposition 2, the individual payoffs in equation (21) are coupled and cannot be evaluated separately. The process requires a backward induction valuation.

4. Conclusion

This article addresses a very important topic of the impact of collateralization on asset prices and risk management. This is the so called plumbing of financial system that affects many outcomes.

We present a comprehensive theoretical framework for pricing collateralized financial contracts based on the fundamental principal and legal structure of CSA agreements. The model can back out differences in asset prices due to collateralized counterparty risk. This is very useful for pricing outstanding defaultable financial contracts.

Empirically, we use a unique proprietary data set to measure the effect of collateralization on pricing and compare it with model-implied prices. We find a quite number of swap contracts that have different collateral arrangements but are similar otherwise. Presumably, differences in swap rates should be largely attributable to differences in counterparty risk. The empirical results show that model-implied prices are quite close to market-quoted prices, which suggests the model is fairly accurate in pricing collateralized contracts.

We find strong evidence that counterparty risk alone plays a significant but not overwhelming role in determining credit-related spreads for collateralized contracts. Only the joint effect of collateralization and credit risk can provide a sufficient explanation for unsecured credit costs. This finding suggests that failure to properly account for collateralization may result in significant mispricing of financial contracts.

Appendix

Proof of Proposition 1: If the contract survives, the survival value is the promised payoff X_T . If the contract defaults, the default payment is $C(T) + \varphi(T)(X_T - C(T))$. The CSA value of the contract is the discounted expectation of the payoffs and is given by

$$V^C(t) = E\{D(t, T)[q(t, T)(C(T) + \varphi(T)(X_T - C(T))) + p(t, T)X_T] | \mathcal{F}_t\} \quad (\text{A1})$$

The collateral posted at time t is given by (14). The value of the collateral at time T becomes $C(T) = C(t) / D(t, T)$, where we consider the time value of money only for the collateral asset. If $V^C(t) > H(t)$ (i.e., $C(t) = V^C(t) - H(t)$), we have

$$V^C(t) = V^N(t) / \bar{I}(t, T) - H(t) \bar{q}(t, T) (1 - \varphi(T)) / \bar{I}(t, T) \quad (\text{A2})$$

where $I(t, T) = D(t, T)[p(t, T) + \varphi(T)q(t, T)]$, $\bar{I}(t, T) = E(I(t, T) | \mathcal{F}_t)$, and $V^N(t) = E[I(t, T)X_T | \mathcal{F}_t]$.

In this case, $V^C(t) > H(t)$ is equivalent to $V^N(t) > H(t)$.

If $V^C(t) \leq H(t)$ (i.e., $C(t) = 0$), we have

$$V^C(t) = V^N(t) \leq H(t) \quad (\text{A3})$$

Combining the two cases of $V^C(t) > H(t)$ and $V^C(t) \leq H(t)$, we have

$$V^C(t) = 1_{V^N(t) \leq H(t)} V^N(t) + 1_{V^N(t) > H(t)} \left[V^N(t) / \bar{I}(t, T) - H(t) \bar{q}(t, T) (1 - \varphi(T)) / \bar{I}(t, T) \right] \quad (\text{A4})$$

or

$$V^C(t) = E[F(t, T) X_T | \mathcal{F}_t] - G(t, T) \quad (\text{A5a})$$

where

$$F(t, T) = \left(1_{V^N(t) \leq H(t)} + 1_{V^N(t) > H(t)} / \bar{I}(t, T) \right) I(t, T) D(t, T) \quad (\text{A5b})$$

$$G(t, T) = 1_{V^N(t) > H(t)} H(t) \bar{q}(t, T) (1 - \varphi(T)) / \bar{I}(t, T) \quad (\text{A5c})$$

Proof of Proposition 2: Let $t = T_0$. On the first payment day, let $V^C(T_1)$ denote the CSA value of the contract excluding the current cash flow X_1 . According to Proposition 1, the CSA value of the contract at t is given by

$$V^C(t) = E[F(T_0, T_1)(X_1 + V^C(T_1)) | \mathcal{F}_t] - G(T_0, T_1) \quad (\text{A6})$$

Similarly, we have

$$V^C(T_1) = E[F(T_1, T_2)(X_2 + V^C(T_2)) | \mathcal{F}_{T_1}] - G(T_1, T_2) \quad (\text{A7})$$

Note that $G(T_0, T_1)$ is \mathcal{F}_{T_1} -measurable. According to the *taking out what is known* and *tower* properties of conditional expectation, we have

$$\begin{aligned} V^C(t) &= E[F(T_0, T_1)(X_1 + V^C(T_1)) | \mathcal{F}_t] - G(T_0, T_1) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^2 E\left[\prod_{j=0}^{i-1} (F(T_j, T_{j+1})) X_i | \mathcal{F}_t\right] + E\left[\prod_{j=0}^1 (F(T_j, T_{j+1})) V^C(T_2) | \mathcal{F}_t\right] \\ &\quad - \sum_{i=0}^1 E\left[\prod_{j=0}^{i-1} (F(T_j, T_{j+1})) G(T_i, T_{i+1}) | \mathcal{F}_t\right] \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A8})$$

By recursively deriving from T_2 forward over T_m , where $V^C(T_m) = X_m$, we have

$$V^C(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m E\left[\prod_{j=0}^{i-1} (F(T_j, T_{j+1})) X_i | \mathcal{F}_t\right] - \sum_{i=0}^{m-1} E\left[\prod_{j=0}^{i-1} (F(T_j, T_{j+1})) G(T_i, T_{i+1}) | \mathcal{F}_t\right] \quad (\text{A9})$$

Proof of Proposition 3: At time T , there are a total of four possible states shown in Table 1. The joint distributions of A and B are given by (18) and the collateral amount posted at time t is given by (19). Depending on whether the value is in the money or out of the money at T , we have the following situations

Case 1: $V^C(t) > H_B(t) > 0$. We have $C(t) = V^C(t) - H_B(t)$ and

$$\begin{aligned} V^C(t) &= E\left\{D(t, T)\left[\left(p_{00}(t, T) + p_{10}(t, T)\right)X_T + \left(p_{01}(t, T) + p_{11}(t, T)\right)\left(C(T) + \varphi_B(T)(X_T - C(T))\right)\right] \middle| \mathcal{F}_t\right\} \\ &= E\left\{D(t, T)\left[p_B(t, T)X_T + q_B(t, T)\left(\varphi_B(T)X_T + \left(V^C(t) - H(t)\right)\left(1 - \varphi_B(T)\right)/D(t, T)\right)\right] \middle| \mathcal{F}_t\right\} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A10a})$$

or

$$V^C(t) = V_B^N(t) / \bar{I}_B(t, T) - H_B(t) \bar{q}_B(t, T) (1 - \varphi_B(T)) / \bar{I}_B(t, T) \quad (\text{A10b})$$

where $V_B^N(t) = E\left[I_B(t, T)X_T \middle| \mathcal{F}_t\right]$. In this case, $V^C(t) > H_B(t) > 0$ is equivalent to $V_B^N(t) > H_B(t)$.

Case 2: $0 \leq V^C(t) \leq H_B(t)$. We have $C(t) = 0$ and

$$V^C(t) = E\left\{D(t, T)\left(p_B(t, T) + q_B(t, T)\varphi_B(T)\right)X_T \middle| \mathcal{F}_t\right\} = V_B^N(t) \quad (\text{A11})$$

In this case, $0 \leq V^C(t) \leq H_B(t)$ is equivalent to $0 \leq V_B^N(t) \leq H_B(t)$

Case 3: $V^C(t) < H_A(t) < 0$. We have $C(t) = V^C(t) - H_A(t)$ and

$$\begin{aligned} V^C(t) &= E\left\{D(t, T)\left[\left(p_{00}(t, T) + p_{01}(t, T)\right)X_T + \left(p_{10}(t, T) + p_{11}(t, T)\right)\left(C(T) + \varphi_A(T)(X_T - C(T))\right)\right] \middle| \mathcal{F}_t\right\} \\ &= E\left\{D(t, T)\left[p_A(t, T)X_T + q_A(t, T)\left(\varphi_A(T)X_T + C(T)\left(1 - \varphi_A(T)\right)\right)\right] \middle| \mathcal{F}_t\right\} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A12a})$$

or

$$V^C(t) = V_A^N(t) / \bar{I}_A(t, T) - H_A(t) \bar{q}_A(t, T) (1 - \varphi_A(T)) / \bar{I}_A(t, T) \quad (\text{A12b})$$

where $V_A^N(t) = E\left[I_A(t, T)X_T \middle| \mathcal{F}_t\right]$. In this case, $V^C(t) < H_A(t) < 0$ is equivalent to $V_A^N(t) < H_A(t)$.

Case 4: $0 \geq V^C(t) \geq H_A(t)$. We have $C(t) = 0$ and

$$V^C(t) = E\left\{D(t, T)\left(p_A(t, T) + q_A(t, T)\varphi_A(T)\right)X_T \middle| \mathcal{F}_t\right\} = V_A^N(t) \quad (\text{A13})$$

In this case, $0 > V^C(t) \geq H_A(t)$ is equivalent to $0 \geq V_A^N(t) \geq H_A(t)$.

Combining the four cases together, we have

$$V^C(t) = E[L(t,T)X_T | \mathcal{F}_t] - M(t,T) \quad (\text{A14a})$$

Where

$$L(t,T) = D(t,T) \left[1_{0 \leq V_B^N(t) \leq H_B(t)} I_B(t,T) + 1_{V_B^N(t) > H_B(t)} I_B(t,T) / \bar{I}_B(t,T) \right. \\ \left. + 1_{0 \geq V_A^N(t) \geq H_A(t)} I_A(t,T) + 1_{V_A^N(t) < H_A(t)} I_A(t,T) / \bar{I}_A(t,T) \right] \quad (\text{A14b})$$

$$M(t,T) = 1_{V_B^N(t) > H_B(t)} H_B(t) \bar{q}_B(t,T) (1 - \varphi_B(T)) / \bar{I}_B(t,T) \\ + 1_{V_A^N(t) < H_A(t)} H_A(t) \bar{q}_A(t,T) (1 - \varphi_A(T)) / \bar{I}_A(t,T) \quad (\text{A14c})$$

where $\bar{I}_j(t,T) = E(I_j(t,T) | \mathcal{F}_t) = E(p_j(t,T) + \varphi_j(T) q_j(t,T) | \mathcal{F}_t)$, $V_j^N(t) = E[I_j(t,T) X_T | \mathcal{F}_t]$, and $j = A$ or B .

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